

The Impact of Use of Expense Information on Financial Statements on Operation Performance in Viet Nam Agricultural Enterprises

Author's Details: ⁽¹⁾Thi Tuyet Do ⁽²⁾Thi Thanh Huong Cao

⁽¹⁾⁽²⁾University of Economics - Technology for Industries, Vietnam

Correspondence: Thi Tuyet Do, 456 Minh Khai, Hai Ba Trung, Ha Noi

Abstract:

UCI has an impact on performance (PER), in which the strongest impact is cost control, followed by profitability, and finally the production cycle. The results of this study will be a reference for businesses to increase their awareness of the importance of CI and impacts of UCI on PER in enterprises. At the same time, it is a reference channel for the state and professional accountancy organizations to provide guidance and orientation in the implementation, application and use of CAS for administration.

Keywords: cost management, managerial support, Vietnamese agricultural enterprises

1. Introduction

Professional accountancy organization IFAC (2009) has emphasized the importance of CI, saying that enterprises need to have a comprehensive understanding of how resources are used and how costs are incurred, CI will provides cost insight for specific activities, products and services. Professional accounting organizations have also begun to pay attention to the importance of CI and have begun to build principles on the CI system to help support corporate governance. IFAC (2009) developed and issued the Evaluating and Improving Costing in Organizations guide, the main content of this tutorial provides general principles about measuring, recording, aggregating, and allocating costs and resources. to objects such as products, activities, customers ..., from which these objects are analyzed, explained, understood deeply and continuously improved and developed. In addition, IFAC (2013) continues to develop and publish a guide to Evaluating the Costing Journey: A Costing Levels Continuum Maturity Model, the main content of this guide covers 12 levels of evolution and development of the system. cost accounting (CAS), from the simple level to the most complex level. In addition, another reputable accounting professional organization in the field of management accounting (IMA) is also interested in this issue and publishes the SMA, the SMA provides international economic practices and guidance to Enterprise applies in managing resources and making reasonable management decisions. In these SMA, the Conceptual Framework for Managerial Costing is very important in building a theoretical framework of costs, this publication provides a theoretical framework for costs for governance, allowing enterprises to identify good CI. best to provide for DN internal decision-making. The goal of this theoretical framework will help businesses design and build a cost model so that managers can successfully apply, thereby developing activities and achieving enterprise goals.

In Vietnam, the practice of UCI serving for governance is also very rich and brings practical results, according to Vnexpress on August 12, 2019, after Xa Chu Chuong Duong was acquired from investors. Thailand has shifted from loss to profit, the performance of Xa Chuong Duong has been more and more positive, mainly due to good cost control. Or as in the case of Vicostone, which has good cost control due to competitive pressure, according to Cafef newspaper dated March 15, 2018, Mr. Ho Xuan Nang, chairman of the board of directors said to solve the cost problem. As input materials increase, the company will try to optimize costs of businesses to keep selling prices stable and improve competitiveness. Moreover, enhancing competitiveness not only comes from the aspect of technology, but also comes from governance. In addition, according to the Investor newspaper, on April 26, 2017, Vingroup implemented a governance revolution, according to Mr. Pham Nhat Vuong, with 5 directions on governance reform, focusing on automation. The cost will be reduced significantly and the cost will be shared by a large number of devices, so the efficiency will be higher. According to the Vietnam Chamber of Commerce and Industry - VCCI on December 25, 2019, Phu Nhuan Jewelry Joint Stock Company (PNJ) announced that the financial situation has been significantly improved thanks to the

restructuring of the portfolio. product and production cost optimization. In addition, the company uses ERP to optimize operating processes, manage losses and save costs.

With the importance of CI being mentioned, discussed and researched in terms of academic and practical research. Researches in Vietnam are also not out of that trend, Nguyen Viet (1997) argues that CI benefits provided by the ABC system such as more accurate and reasonable cost calculation, thereby helping managers out. better decision. To control costs better, according to Nguyen Xuan Hung (2003), providing CI is based on the difference between actual costs and normed costs to assess the responsibilities of individuals and departments involved. Huynh Loi (2009) argues that the indirect cost allocation serves for cost control and effectiveness evaluation, and for product and service selling prices. The CI needs to be linked with governance functions such as planning, control, evaluation and decision making. More recent studies gradually began to mention factors affecting CAS such as Ho My Hanh (2013), Pham Hong Hai (2013), Tran Thi Thu Huong (2014), Dao Thuy Ha (2015), Tran Ngoc Hung (2016), Nguyen Phong Nguyen et al (2016), Nguyen Phong Nguyen & Tran Thi Trinh (2018) all commented and discovered the importance of CI in governance, according to management innovation perspectives. These studies lay an important foundation for the next research in Vietnam. In general, the research on CI in governance has initially been approached from many different perspectives, but with the need to improve governance capacity is still a practical issue in each address, scope and type. DN image.

In agricultural enterprises it is extremely important to use cost information on financial statements to improve operational efficiency.

2. Literature review

Ho My Hanh (2013) mentioned the existence of a relationship between CAS and FER. Nguyen Phong Nguyen & Tran Thi Trinh (2018) believe that using international economic information has a strong impact on PER. Research on ABC's impact on PER has not been studied in terms of both case and quantitative research in Vietnam. Therefore, the research direction on ABC affecting PER in Vietnam probably starts from a real case study in an enterprise that has applied ABC, thereby summarizing the lessons learned about the advantages and disadvantages. and the benefits that ABC brings. After a relatively large number of enterprises have applied ABC, quantitative research is appropriate. In a nutshell, for this research direction to be feasible in Vietnam today, the discovery of the effectiveness of a CAS, or the degree of using CAS, the degree of UCI affecting PER as Mahama & Cheng (2013), Nguyen Phong Nguyen et al (2016, 2018) suggest the theoretical model.

Cagwin et al. (2002) also found that firms had a significant improvement in financial results when ABC was used concurrently with strategic tools such as JIT or TQM compared to businesses without ABC. There is a positive relationship between ABC and improved ROI when implemented in a business with complex and diverse industries, in a relatively high cost environment. There is an indication that other permissible conditions (good IT, little excess capacity and competitive environment) affect ABC's efficiency. The author also acknowledges that to measure success, including satisfaction with ABC and the financial benefits gained from ABC are predictors of financial performance improvement. In addition, Ittner et al. (2002) found a positive sign, but "modest" the relationship between ABC use and production results, whereby using ABC helps businesses improve through the following aspects: ROA, production cycle, and cost are reduced.

Sanford (2009) said that firms that use ABC have higher asset turnover than firms that do not use ABC. Similarly, research by James & Elmezughi (2010), found that the leading firms in low cost using both ABC and BSC have financial results, perform customers, perform innovation better than businesses. other

The current direction of overseas research is about UCI and the benefits of UCI in contributing to PER have also been done quite a lot. However, the studies are mainly case studies and descriptive statistical methods such as Gagne & Discenza (1993), Cooper & Slagmulder (1999), Uyar (2010), Tobi et al. (2015), Almeida & Cunha (2017). In recent years, only the emerging research of Ilemona & Sunday (2019) has started to use quantitative

methods to examine the impact of UCI on corporate profits. Therefore, in overseas this research direction requires many quantitative models to measure the impact of UCI on PER in financial and non-financial aspects. In addition, the research direction of factors affecting UCI focuses mainly on factors outside of enterprises, factors within enterprises are less mentioned, so more research is needed to focus on investigating the factors within enterprises that affect UCI.

Research abroad is now also tending to study the effectiveness of a CAS as Shoute (2009). The effectiveness of a CAS is measured by two basic aspects: (a) level UCI degree for governance, (b) CAS satisfaction. In addition, Pike et al. (2011) proposed measuring the effectiveness of ABC through five aspects, including cost accuracy, balance of benefits and costs, ABC's impact, use of CI and influence on decision-making. This direction study was also started by Nguyen Phong Nguyen et al (2016) in Vietnam by measuring CAS usage in Vietnamese hospitals. UCI is a component of the CAS concept of success and effectiveness, so research on UCI is the direction of research on CAS success and effectiveness. Accordingly, Mahama & Cheng (2013) measures the effectiveness of CAS by UCI level for governance through four aspects (a) control and cost reduction, (b) redesign and improvement, (c) budget book (d) evaluation of results. Although slightly different, Shoute's (2009) measurement of UCI has nine purposes: cost reduction, price determination, performance evaluation, cost control, budgeting, profit analysis. customers, decide the number of products to produce, design new products, evaluate inventory. By measuring the degree of UCI or measuring the effectiveness of CAS by previous researchers, the measurement of these concepts according to the author of the thesis can be collected and measured in the context of Vietnam. .

The role factor of CI, IT, the author of the thesis chooses from the research direction of the success of CAS to be the independent factor affecting the level of UCI, while UCI is a component of the concept of success. CAS, if UCI is separated as an independent concept, whether these two factors have influence on UCI, if they do, it proves that UCI is an important, indispensable component to contribute to the success of CAS. In addition, Mahama & Cheng (2013) have not mentioned and discovered these two factors, so whether these two factors have an impact on UCI to make CAS more effective or not.

In Vietnam, previous researchers have laid a very important foundation in theory when talking about the role and benefits of CI through researchers such as Pham Van Duoc (1997), Nguyen Viet (1997), Ha Xuan Thach (1999), Nguyen Xuan Hung (2003), Huynh Loi (2009), Nguyen Phong Nguyen et al (2016, 2018). Accordingly, in Vietnam, it is necessary to continue research in this direction according to the quantitative model to further develop the role and benefits of UCI, which will help to improve and improve PER. Data collection in this research direction is likely to be easier and more advantageous than ABC because enterprises still maintain CI and CAS systems for governance without necessarily applying ABC. It is therefore highly probable that the collection of the sufficient sample sizes needed to perform analysis and test of the proposed model in this direction is considered feasible in the Vietnamese context. In addition, studies on UCI affecting PER focus on UCI in companies that apply ABC, so whether in Vietnam environment there are few companies applying ABC, does UCI affect PER? . The purpose of this test to help clarify the problem is that enterprises that do not apply ABC may still maintain a CAS for governance and UCI can contribute to improving the PER.

Some research models on UCI in Vietnam have also discovered that UCI in hospitals has a positive impact on employee performance (Nguyen Phong Nguyen et al., 2016). Thus, UCI needs to expand the scope of research in manufacturing and service enterprises operating in other industries and discover more about the impact of UCI on PER in other aspects such as production cycle, ability to test cost and profit control.

Gordon & Sylvester (1999) found that ABC positively affects competitive advantage and profitability. ABC cost improvement is mentioned by Kennedy & Affleck-Graves (2001). Apart from the financial aspects, Ittner et al. (2002) found that ABC impacts non-financial aspects such as production cycle and cost reduction. Narrow research directions have also shown that UCI will help negotiate purchases more effectively through research by Abbeele et al. (2009). A change in CAS also contributes to an increase in PER, but will have a strong impact

on PER when the selling pricing system changes accordingly (Laitinen, 2014). In another analysis, Henri et al. (2016) said that CI on the environment also has an impact on improving the financial status of businesses.

With the results achieved, studies have tried to prove the application of a CAS in general or in particular ABC, as well as the success and effectiveness of a CAS, will contribute to improving the PER of the enterprise in terms of financial and non-financial. The results of the study have also shown the practical benefits of applying and operating a CAS in practice, contributing to motivating enterprises to apply a CAS successfully and effectively to bring high results to enterprises. In Vietnam, these will be valuable documents for businesses to refer to and understand clearly about the application and selection of a suitable CAS for their businesses.

Costing is a key concept in the design of CAS, as well as the selection of aggregation methods and cost calculation that serve many different purposes. There are many different views on the cost definition of theoretical researchers and professional organizations of accounting. First of all is the viewpoint of Horngren et al. (2012) definition: a cost is a resource that is scarce or spent to achieve a specific goal. Cost is usually measured in the currency, which is the amount paid to buy goods or services. Professional accountancy organizations also come up with definitions from their own point of view, such as the American International Economic Association (IMA, 2014) that costs are measured in terms of money through (i) using sources. force or output to achieve a particular regulatory purpose, or (ii) create a resource or product to be supplied without using it. Or the International Federation of Accountants (IFAC, 2009) is defined as follows: cost is the monetary value of resources used to achieve a goal, such as the manufacture of a product or service. or perform an activity, product or service to provide but not use them.

3. Theory

3.1. Contingency Theory

Random theory covers how best to organize a company (Weill & Olson 1989). Random theory is a branch of behavioral theory that shares the same view that there is no best way to organize or lead a company, but the optimal way is to act randomly according to internal and external situations. apart at a time (Fiedler, 1964). The random theory studies in the accounting field such as Chenhall (2003) argue that environment, technology, company structure and size affect the design of the management control system (MCS). In addition to the MCS-focused studies, another line of research, mainly trying to identify the random factors involved in the design of management information systems (MIS) has reviewed this theory and concluded It is argued that the random variables that have been studied often include strategy, firm structure, size, environment and technology. Furthermore, randomization theory is also studied extensively through assuming the relationship between MIS design and MIS's effectiveness, and studying the relationship between the effectiveness of MIS and the effectiveness of the organization (Weill & Olson, 1989).

In addition to a series of theoretical stochastic studies involving MCS and MIS, studies have also attempted to identify random factors to explain the structure of CAS (Al-Omiri & Drury, 2007). CAS is considered to be a subset of MCS and MIS, so this theory also explains the specific design choices related to CAS. For example, Chenhall's (1986) study provides some evidence from the relationship between uncertainty and the extent of accounting information. Or research by Cooper (1988), the author argues that the optimal level of CAS is not only dependent on cost measurement, cost error and product diversity, but also affected by many factors. factors (eg competition intensity). The initial randomized theoretical research papers related to CASs focused on contextual factors affecting ABC application or non-application (Clarke et al., 1999). The most common random factors studied were product diversity, cost structure, size, and other variables, such as competitiveness, level of fulfillment, quality. IT, the level of advanced technology and a competitive strategy have also been studied.

3.2. Information Economics Theory

Economic information theory is a branch of microeconomic theory that focuses on how information affects economic problems and economic decisions. Information is so special that it is easy to generate, but hard to believe. Information is easily spread but is difficult to control and influences many decisions.

Establishing and constructing economic information is an essential tool of accounting researchers, which is the design of models related to accounting in general and international economy in particular. Feltham was one of the first researchers on economic information and evaluation of accounting information systems (Feltham & Demski, 1970). Demski (1972) is research author on information analysis, focusing on information choice and control decisions. Research by Callahan & Gabriel (1998) relating to issues CI provides for economic management and decision-making. Researchers have asserted that the CAS provides a variety of highly accurate cost reports or the impact accuracy that add value to decisions. Researchers believe that companies that are under competitive pressure, offering a cost-leading strategy when increasing the CI accuracy of a product, profit will increase, while firms compete on the basis of Product differentiation does not benefit from increased product cost accuracy.

Research by Eldenburg (1994) relating to CI provision in hospital. The study deals with cost management in hospitals, examining the impact on physicians to reduce the resources used in clinical practice, and providing CI on treating patients to doctors is important. Similarly, Larcker (1981) concludes that managers have relevant CI references that can be used in making strategic capital budgeting decisions. These results suggest that the value and degree of UCI may depend on firms due to factors of product competition, market structure and market strategy.

4. Research Methodology

Research topics are conducted according to mixed methods, including qualitative and quantitative.

Qualitative research: The first step of the thesis is to select, analyze and synthesize from previous studies to find research gaps. In this step, the most important thing is to find out the main research concept from which to sketch out the expected research model, including independent, dependent variables and relationships among variables through research hypotheses. assist. In the next step, the author builds a draft scale for the independent and dependent variables in the research model. To build scales for variables, the author of the thesis selects and synthesizes from previous studies to build a draft scale. The next step is qualitative research through interviews with a number of experts to determine the suitability of the model, draft scales in Vietnamese conditions.

Quantitative research: performing scale test by analyzing the reliability of Cronbach's α and EFA to form a set of scales for the research model. The scales continue to be tested by CFA affirmative factor analysis to prepare for research model testing. After testing the scale in the research model, the research model and hypothesis are tested by the SEM linear structure model. In addition, the Bootstrap method is used to verify the reliability of the estimates in the official research model.

5. Research results

Table 1: EFA PER - production cycle

KMO and Bartlett's Test						
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.						.800
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity			Approx. Chi-Square		368.411	
			df		6	
			Sig.		.000	
Tổng AVE - Total Variance Explained						
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.721	68.025	68.025	2.721	68.025	68.025

2	.530	13.254	81.279			
3	.434	10.855	92.134			
4	.315	7.866	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 2: EFA PER scale - cost control

KMO and Bartlett's Test						
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.						.781
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square					353.761
	df					6
	Sig.					.000
Tổng AVE - Total Variance Explained						
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.658	66.455	66.455	2.658	66.455	66.455
2	.595	14.878	81.332			
3	.454	11.349	92.681			
4	.293	7.319	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 3: EFA scale of PER - profit

KMO and Bartlett's Test						
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.						.766
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square					241.285
	df					6
	Sig.					.000
Tổng AVE - Total Variance Explained						
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.390	59.746	59.746	2.390	59.746	59.746
2	.691	17.265	77.011			
3	.507	12.681	89.692			
4	.412	10.308	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 4: EFA and PER factors

KMO and Bartlett's Test: 0.821			
Tổng AVE - Total Variance Explained: 66.098			
Ma trận xoay nhân tố: Rotated Component Matrix ^a			
	Component		
	1	2	3
CKSX2	.848		
CKSX3	.820		
CKSX4	.789		
CKSX1	.770		
KSCP2		.822	
KSCP1		.814	
KSCP4		.770	
KSCP3		.709	

CFA results together with PER factors

5. Conclusion

Production cycle scale, cost control and profitability have indicators that are all satisfactory. Moreover, in terms of the content of the scale, the previous studies all support the observed variables of this scale. Overall, with this result, the PER scales including production cycle, cost control and profitability are satisfactory for the study in the Vietnamese context.

UCI directly affects PER such as cost control (standardized regression weight is 0.388), profit (normalized regression weight is 0.236) and production cycle (normalized regression weight is 0.183) . Thus, we can confirm that UCI is very important and contributes to improve the enterprise's PER.

To achieve efficiency in collecting, processing and enhancing UCI, businesses need to have a strong IT system, especially software with CI processing functions that meet administrative requirements, such as ERP software is written and programmed to process CI according to the standard cost method, target cost, ABC ... Because theory and practice researchers all emphasize the importance of CI used to manage. CI can be used at a high level, providing the ability for managers at all levels to align with the organization's goals for enterprise optimization (IMA, 2014). Utilizing target CI by allocating target costs across regions responsible for cost reduction helps ensure that only profitable products reach the market (Slagmulder, 1999). CI will help businesses improve decision-making, to analyze and control product profits, measure PER and improve operations (Shil & Pramanik, 2012).

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